

SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 10.5: 1ST UPDATED COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN

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Public summary of
confidential report

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Due Date: 31.12.2023

Submission Date: 18.12.2023

Accepted Date: 29.12.2023

Deliverable Reference: D10.5

Work Package / Task:

WP10 / Task 10.5

Keywords:

Communication, Key Performance
Indicators, KPI, algae, macroalgae,
seaweed, commercialisation

Summary:

The first updated communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan (CDEP) analyses the communication, dissemination exploitation and follow-up activities of the SeaMark CDE strategies and its impacts, as well as proposes changes in this strategy going forward. It offers a set of methodologies, indicators, and next steps to maximize the impact of the resources (budget, staff, time) allocated to these tasks. A main part of the success has been the CDE toolkit, with comprehensive templates, guidelines and material for all partners to use in order to maximise CDE and create cohesive communication. Also, an update of the platform for market exploitation in BlueBioMatch is described as the chosen platform and merged with the Industry Purchasing Group (IPG).

The indicators include the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) selected in the "Deliverable 10.1: Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan", a selection of indicators across digital channels (websites, social media) and are also established according to goals (audience impressions, interactions, virality, and activity). Quantitative indicators on the number of activities and the size of their estimated audience are also included. A set of actions are suggested to increase the impact of the project on its target audience. The first updated plan includes:

- I. Update SWOT analysis
- II. Review and update strategic communication actions (SCAs)
- III. Review and update timeline
- IV. Update follow-up measures
- V. Results
- VI. Conclusion and next steps

SeaMark partners have actively participated in a range of conferences, attending around 40 conferences in the first 18 months of the project. Some of these includes the Nordic Seaweed conference 2022, Aquaculture Europe 2022/23, EU4Algae 2022, International Seaweed Symposium 2022/23, World Seaweed Seminar, Seagriculture Europe 2022/23, Ocean Days in Brest, Ocean Week in Monaco DG Mare in Pari, Food Ingredient Europe 2023, Mission Arena in Sweden.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060379. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor REA can be held responsible for them.

Furthermore, the initial 18 months of the SeaMark communication plan have demonstrated successful implementation across various facets, and the adaptive approach taken ensures alignment with evolving project experiences and knowledge. The groundwork laid during this period positions SeaMark favourably for continued success in subsequent phases of the project.